

Piezoelectric effects and its potential implement in rural Nepali areas to solve electricity crisis during rainy seasons

Abstract

Nepal faces electricity shortage in rural Nepali areas during the rainy season because of landslide, heavy wind which creates a problem in electricity transmission through poles and wires. This research paper explores piezoelectric effect as an alternative micro-energy source for rural Nepal. This study outlines the working principle of piezoelectricity and discusses its potential implementation in rural areas.

1. Introduction

Rural Nepali areas have limited electricity access due to limited grid expansions, seasonal hydropower variations and geographic restrictions. While solar exists, it cannot fully meet the electricity needed rainy seasons in lack of enough sunlight. Piezoelectric energy harvesting offers a small scale but sustainable way to produce electricity in region with high rain and pedestrian activity.

2. Understanding the Piezoelectric Effect

2.1 Definition

The piezoelectric effect is the ability of certain materials like quartz, and ceramic to generate a electric charge when mechanical stress is applied to them. When pressure deforms the crystal lattice, charge displacement creates an electric potential.

2.2 Mathematical Idea

The electrical charge(Q) generated is proportional to the Force applied:

$$Q = d \times F$$

Where:

Q = electric charge

d = piezoelectric coefficient

F = force applied

This means stronger forces or more frequent pressure produces more electricity.

3. Relevance to Rural Nepal

Rural Nepal has high levels of daily human walking and high level of rain in rainy seasons. Footpath, suspension bridges, school routes experiences consistent pedestrian traffic. These places offer opportunity to install piezo tiles that convert foot pressure into electricity. While rooftop offer opportunity to install vibrationally inducing piezo elements.

4. Feasibility and Challenges

Advantages

operates without sunlight or water
Low maintenance once installed
Environmentally clean energy source

Limitations

Low energy output per step
High cost of piezoelectric tiles
Durability challenges in Nepal's climate
Need for technical awareness and initial investment

5. Conclusion

Piezoelectric electricity harvesting shows a promising solution for small scale electricity generation in rural Nepal. Its ability to generate electricity from vibration of rooftop during rain, everyday movements such as walking makes it suitable for high rain and footfall areas such as home, bridges, steps. Although it cannot completely replace the traditional way of harvesting energy such as hydropower it can work quite well as a supplementary solution. With technological advancements and reduced costs, piezoelectric systems could become an important component of Nepal's renewable energy strategy.

6. Reference

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